

A REFINED HIGHER-ORDER THEORY FOR LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES

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A refined higher-order shear deformation theory of laminated composite plates is presented. The theory accounts for a parabolic variations of the transverse shear strains and the transverse deflections through the thickness of the plate. Exact closed-form solutions of symmetric cross-ply laminates are obtained and the results are compared with three-dimensional elasticity solutions, first-order shear deformation theory solutions and other higher-order shear deformation theory solutions. The present theory predicts the deflections and stresses more accurately when compared to the first-order theory and other higher-order theory.

INTRODUCTION

A number of articles dealing with the transverse shear deformation have appeared in the literature. These are too numerous to review here. We only cite some classical⁽¹⁻⁹⁾ papers and those which constitute a background for the present paper. The theories that account for transverse shear deformations can be classified into two major classes on the basis of assumed fields: (1) stress based theories^(2-4,8,9) and (2) displacement based theories^(1-5,7). The stress-based theories are derived from assumed stress fields, which are assumed to vary linearly over the thickness of the plate. The transverse normal and shear stresses are then derived from the equilibrium equations of the three-dimensional problem in the theory of elasticity. The governing equations of the theory are derived using a stationary variational theorem. The displacement based theories are derived from an assumed displacement field. The governing equations are derived using the principle of minimum total potential energy.

The theory used in the present work comes under the class of displacement based theories. In Reissner-Mindlin type theories^(1,5-7,10-14), the displacement field accounts for linear or higher-order variations of midplane displacements through thickness. In higher-order theories, an additional dependent unknown is introduced into the theory with each additional power of the thickness coordinate. In addition, these shear deformation theories do not satisfy the conditions of zero transverse shear stresses on the top and bottom surfaces of the plate, and require a shear correction to the transverse shear stiffnesses. Recently, Levinson⁽¹⁵⁾, Murthy⁽¹⁶⁾ and Reddy⁽¹⁷⁻¹⁹⁾ presented refined plate theories that use the idea of Basset¹ in expanding displacements in the powers of the thickness coordinate. The main novelty of these works is to expand the in-plane displacements as cubic functions of the thickness coordinate, treat the transverse deflection as a function of the x and y coordinates and satisfy the conditions of zero transverse shear strains on the top and bottom surfaces of the plate. Murthy's work differs from Levinson's in two respects: first, Murthy uses average displacements through thickness; secondly, the theory is also developed for laminated plates. The work of Reddy differs from the other two in that the governing equations are derived from the principle of virtual work. The present development is to expand the in-plane displacements as cubic functions of the thickness coordinate and the transverse deflection as a parabolic function of the thickness coordinate. The governing

equations are also derived from the principle of virtual work. To illustrate the accuracy of the present theory, exact solutions are presented for symmetrically laminated cross-ply rectangular plates.

KINEMATICS

The present refined theory uses a displacement approach, much like in the Reissner-Mindlin type theories. It not only satisfies the conditions that the transverse shear stresses vanish on the plate surfaces but also accounts for the effect of the variation of the transverse deflection along the thickness.

The displacement field is written as

$$U = U_0 + Z \left(\psi_x - \frac{z}{2} \frac{\partial \psi_z}{\partial x} - \frac{4}{3} \left(\frac{z}{h} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x} + \psi_x + \frac{h^2}{4} \frac{\partial \epsilon_z}{\partial x} \right) \right)$$

$$V = U_0 + Z \left(\psi_x - \frac{z}{2} \frac{\partial \psi_z}{\partial x} - \frac{4}{3} \left(\frac{z}{h} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x} + \psi_x + \frac{h^2}{4} \frac{\partial \epsilon_z}{\partial x} \right) \right)$$

$$W = W_0 + Z \psi_z + z^2 \epsilon_z$$

EQUILIBRIUM EQUATIONS

Here we use the principle of virtual displacements to derive the equilibrium equations appropriate for the displacement field and constitutive equations. The principle of virtual displacements can be written in analytical form as

$$\int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \int_{\Omega} (\sigma_1 \delta \epsilon_1 + \sigma_2 \delta \epsilon_2 + \sigma_3 \delta \epsilon_3 + \sigma_4 \delta \epsilon_4 + \sigma_5 \delta \epsilon_5 + \sigma_6 \delta \epsilon_6) dAdz - \int_{\Omega} q \delta w dx dy = 0$$

EXACT SOLUTIONS FOR SYMMETRIC CROSS-PLY PLATES

We consider the exact solutions for simply supported, symmetric cross-ply rectangular plates. The Navier approach is used.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The three-dimensional elasticity solutions of Pagano⁽²⁰⁾ and Pagano and Hatfield⁽²¹⁾ for simply supported rectangular plates under sinusoidal loading are used to assess the improvement by the present theory. Table 1-3 contain nondimensionalized deflections and stresses for the three problems. For Problem 1 and 2, the results obtained using the present

Theory are compared with those obtained by three-dimensional elasticity theory⁽²⁰⁾⁽²¹⁾, the higher-order shear deformation plate theory (HSDPT)⁽¹⁸⁾ and the first-order shear deformation theory⁽²²⁾, respectively. The exact stresses σ_1 , σ_2 and σ_6 computed using the constitutive equations of the present theory are greatly improved over the results obtained using the first-order and classical plate theory and are also more accurate than those obtained by the higher-order shear deformation plate theory⁽¹⁸⁾ when the ratio a/h is less than 10. The shear stresses obtained using constitutive equations are not as accurate as the stresses σ_1 , σ_2 , σ_6 . This error might be due to the fact that the stress continuity across each layer interface is not imposed in the present theory. As in the case of the Classical Plate Theory (CPT), the transverse shear stresses can also be determined by integrating equilibrium equations (of

three-dimensional elasticity in the absence of body forces) with respect to the thickness coordinate:

$$\sigma_5 = - \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\sigma_{x,x} + \sigma_{xy,y}) dz$$

$$\sigma_4 = - \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\sigma_{y,y} + \sigma_{xy,x}) dz$$

The foregoing approach not only gives single-value shear stresses at the interfaces but yields excellent results in comparison with the three-dimensional solutions. Typical stress distributions of $\sigma_5 = \sigma_{xz}$ and $\sigma_4 = \sigma_{yz}$ through the thickness ($a/h=10$) are shown in Fig.2. It is also shown that the shear stresses obtained by the present theory is more accurate than those obtained using the higher-order shear deformation plate theory when the ratio a/h is equal to 4. According to Whitney and Pagano⁽¹²⁾, the severity of shear deformation effects also depends on the material anisotropy of the layers. The exact maximum deflections of simply supported four-layer(0/90/90/0) cross-ply laminates are compared in Fig.3 for various ratios of moduli, E_1/E_2 (for a given thickness, $a/h=10$). The CPT underpredicts the deflections even at lower ratios of moduli.

CONCLUSIONS

An improved higher-order shear deformation theory that gives parabolic variation of the transverse shear strains and the transverse deflections is presented. It still can satisfy the zero tangential traction boundary conditions on the surfaces of the plate. Exact closed-form solutions of symmetric cross-ply laminates are obtained. From the results in Table 1-2 one can calculate that the present theory, in general, gives more accurate results than the first-order shear deformation theory when compared to the three-dimensional elasticity solution. It can also be shown that the results obtained by the present theory are better than those obtained using the higher-order shear deformation plate theory when the ratio a/h is less than 10. The present theory gives, relatively speaking, faster convergent solution when compared to the FSDT results, as can be seen from Table 3. The results for uniform loading should serve as reference for finite-element analyses.

The results reported herein were obtained during an investigation supported by the National Science Foundation of China. The support is gratefully acknowledged.